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Implementing Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (USPV) Technique for Evaluating the Influence of Cement Type and Content on Durability of Roller Compacted Concrete (RCC)

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ABSTRACT

Implementing nondestructive testing for rigid pavement is essential for quality control and reservation of the pavement surface. The USPV was used to monitor the deterioration of the RCC quality which was prepared in the laboratory with three percentages of cement (10, 12, and 16) % and two types of cement, (ordinary portland cement OPC and sulphate resistant cement SRC). Slab specimens were prepared and divided into three groups. The first group was subjected to 60 cycles of sulphate attack, the second group practiced 60 cycles of (freezing-thawing), while the third group was subjected to 60 cycles of (wetting-drying). The rate of decline in the USPV throughout the durability cycles was monitored and modelled. The superior performance of the SRC was detected among the durability cycles regardless of the cement content. It was concluded that using 12 % of SRC after 60 cycles exhibited higher pulse velocity of (14.2, 11.1, and 8.5) % when the specimens practiced (sulphate attack, freezing-thawing, and wetting-drying) respectively as compared with specimens prepared with OPC. The obtained mathematical models could be implemented to verify the deterioration in the quality of roller compacted concrete through the tested durability variables.

Keywords: Roller compacted concrete. rigid pavement, sulphate resistant cement. portland cement, pulse velocity, sulphate attack, freezing, wetting

INTRODUCTION

Rambabu et al., [1] developed a heavily-loaded Roller compacted concrete. The mechanical properties such as shrinkage strains, and abrasion were analyzed for the microstructure. Fatigue results and stress variation proved that Roller compacted concrete prepared with 13 % cement exhibited better stress absorption capability and can be used as a pavement slab for heavy loaded pavements. Chen et al., [2] presented a method of passive-active joint ultrasonic pulse velocity monitoring for concrete. The time-frequency-space multi-parameter response characteristics of passive and active signals were studied in relation to the damage initiation in concrete. It was revealed that such method provides an idea of evaluating the damage state of concrete more quantitatively and actively than traditional methods. It was concluded that the microscopic damage model of concrete based on the amplitude, and penetrating wave velocity agrees with the damage process of concrete. Zhang et al., [3] designed a set of active waveguide systems to improve the data quality of ultrasonic pulse emission monitoring. The deformation and failure process data of the active waveguide model was verified through comparative experiments with the passive waveguide model, and the signal characteristics of the active waveguide were verified. It was concluded that the evolution of ultrasonic signals in the active waveguide model can evaluate failure morphological characteristics. The ultrasonic testing method (UTM) was used by Dai et al., [4] to examine the characteristics of ultrasonic parameters of bedded shale. The assessment involved analyzing the strain-based method to determine the thresholds for damage stress. Damage thresholds were detected and identified by UTM. Abbas et al., [5] assessed weathered sandstone composite samples using ultrasonic pulses. The deformation behavior was monitored

following (energy, velocity, and amplitude) responses of ultrasonic waves. The intensity of energy reflects the interaction with progressive deformation. The ultrasonic parameters (energy and amplitude) reflected a substantial alteration, during the plastic deformation. Schumacher and Niederleithinger, [6] proposed a combined approach based on active ultrasonic stress wave monitoring techniques for application to concrete structures. It was revealed that the known source at a known location is employed at a specified time under ultrasonic pulse. Such technique is based on the wave motion in solids. It was concluded that implementation of this technique can provide a more comprehensive picture of ongoing damaged progression and fracture processes. Saeedifar et al., [7] used active and passive ultrasound-based health monitoring methods for assessing the impact of damage of composite structures. Ultrasonic technique was employed during the loading and reloading phases to specify the damage type and monitor the critical damage occurrence. The prospect of regulating concrete's internal curing based on real-time data to track the intended concrete performance is discussed by Korda et al. [8]. It was stated that initiation of shrinkage cracking was mitigated before and after using admixture which provides internal curing for several hours after casting. It was revealed that such action takes place in the microstructure and is difficult to monitor. However, it is accompanied by high pulse wave recordings enabling, therefore, the monitoring of the process. Toutounchi et al., [9] evaluated the roller-compacted concrete in freezing conditions using the results of pulse velocity test. The ultrasonic speed of roller compacted concrete samples declined with an increasing number of freezing-thaw cycles due to increasing percentages of weight loss. It was concluded that there was a good correlation between the findings of

USPV values and other physical tests, while it was possible to predict the behavior of RCC samples using this test. The experimental investigation results of USPV tests on roller compacted concrete pavement material were provided by Rao et al. [10]. Lower values of pulse velocity were shown when fly ash was introduced as additive regardless of the curing period. Relationships between compressive strength and USPV and Dynamic Elastic Modulus were proposed. Sarsam, [11] used two types of aggregates (rounded and crushed) for preparation of roller compacted concrete. Specimens were tested for ultrasound pulse velocity, bulk density, flexural and compressive strength. It was concluded that the pulse velocity increases by (19.3, and 49.7) % and (28.8, and 66.6) % when the cement content rises from (10 to 12, and 16) % respectively for mixtures with crushed and rounded aggregates. Li et al., [12] proposed a method for correcting the evaluation of concrete by implementing ultrasound techniques under different stress levels. The validation was conducted through uniaxial graded loading tests. The test results showed that the elastic wave velocity has a significant correlation with the stress levels. The larger the size of coarse aggregate of the concrete samples, the smaller the final wave velocity in the instability stage. Yu et al., [13] reported that the ultrasound pulse characteristics of concrete are governed by the properties of its components. The water-cement ratio plays a significant role in the mechanical properties and components of concrete. The ultrasound pulse characteristics of concrete were discussed considering with various water-cement ratio through frequency domain analysis and parameter analysis. A damage evaluation model of concrete was established based on ultrasound pulse events. It was concluded that ultrasound pulse parameters can characterize the failure stages process (initial, stable, and active) of concrete. Wu

et al., [14] assessed the ultrasound pulse characteristics of concrete with different aggregate size distributions. Parameters such as compressive strain, fracture energies, and maximum aggregate size of different concretes were discussed and measured. The test results indicated that the failure process can be illustrated by the characteristics of ultrasound signals from concrete. Anwar et al., [15] investigated the properties of concrete prepared with ordinary Portland cement and sulphate resistant cement with the aid of pulse velocity, it was found that mixtures with sulphate resistant cement provided higher pulse velocity than that of ordinary Portland cement mixtures. Zhao et al., [16] investigated the ultrasound pulse properties of concrete under sulfate attack conditions. The results showed that the concrete specimens had experienced two stages of deterioration: an enhancement stage and a subsequent deterioration stage and indicated that the exponent can accurately characterize the degree of concrete degradation under sulfate attack. Liu et al., [17] explored the parameters of the ultrasound pulse signal characteristic and its damage evolution in the concrete damage process. The ultrasound phenomenon was expressed using energy activity coefficient. Ospitia et al., [18] stated that ultrasound pulse is sensitive to the original strain field, and it allows projections to the final damage. The test results indicated monotonic relations between strain field and ultrasound pulse parameters at small fractions of the load and highlighted the potential of using ultrasound pulse complemented with other techniques for monitoring and predicting the behavior of structural materials. Lv et al., [19] assessed the performance and freeze–thaw damage characteristics of concrete based on ultrasound pulse technologies and mechanical tests. Damage characteristics due to Freeze–thaw cycles were evaluated through mass loss analysis, compressive mechanical

testing, and ultrasonic pulse velocity testing. The outcomes of the testing indicated that there is a parabola fitting pattern which represent the relationships between cumulative mass loss, ultrasonic wave velocity, compressive strength, and freeze-thaw cycles. It was concluded that understanding of freeze-thaw damage characteristics of concrete is based on acoustic parameters and compressive properties and can enhance its performance through degradation and damage status for concrete. Lian et al., [20] investigated the influence of freeze-thaw cycles on the cracking and mechanical properties of concrete. A freeze-thaw cycle (-20 to 20) °C was adopted and monitored through ultrasound pulse technique. The changes in the elastic modulus, compressive strength, and strain before and after various freeze-thaw cycles were analyzed. It was concluded that elastic modulus and brittleness of the concrete specimens declined gradually with the increase in freeze-thaw cycles. Xu et al., [21] used ultrasound pulse techniques for evaluating the freezing-thawing characteristics of concrete. Test results showed that the accumulative energy in concrete declines with increasing the freezing-thawing cycles. Park et al., [22] stated that non-linear ultrasonic techniques are favoured for detecting microscale damage of concrete under repeated freeze-thaw conditions due to their high sensitivity to microcracks. Such technique was implemented to assess the damage of cement mortar specimens which practiced different freeze-thaw cycles. The freeze-thaw damage was also evaluated with conventional compressive strength tests. A correlation was established for assessing the damage at the early stages and at later stages as the damage progressed. A reliable results were produced. Zhao et al., [23] assessed the deterioration of concrete under the coupling action of sulfate attack and freeze-thaw cycles with the aid of

ultrasound pulse signals generated during concrete failure. Test results showed that with the increase of cycle times, the energy distribution exponent and shear cracks through failure process of concrete gradually increases. Cao et al., [24] assessed the ultrasound pulse characteristic parameters of concrete when practicing different freeze-thaw cycles. Data were analyzed with the correlation parameter method. It was concluded that with the increase of freeze-thaw cycles number, more serious spalling of the concrete surface could be noticed, the rate of mass loss increases while the amplitude of the first wave declines, indicating more obvious internal cracks of the concrete and more serious damage. Wang et al., [25] assessed effect of wet-dry cycles on the strength deterioration of concrete under ultrasound pulse technology. Concrete specimens were loaded with various levels of stress and subjected to seven wet-dry cycles. The deterioration of strength of the concrete was evaluated and analyzed by uniaxial compression and through an ultrasonic pulse technique. Test results show that the cumulative energy of concrete decreases with the progression of wet-dry cycles. Saliba et al., [26] applied ultrasonic pulse technique for estimating the concrete progressive deterioration during 25 wetting/drying cycles. The test results declared that the degradation of concrete starts during the first cycle with visible cracks on the surface of the specimens. Considerable loss of mechanical properties of concrete was observed after 25 cycles. The cumulative acoustic activity was effectively used to assess crack propagation through different damage progression phases and indicates premature damage for concrete specimens subjected to wet-dry cycles. Zhu et al., [27] analyzed the degradation of concrete and the process and mechanism of concrete crack extension through its fracture under wetting-drying cycles with

the aid of ultrasound pulse techniques and three point bending test.

The aim of the present work is to monitor the deterioration of the quality of RCC mixture through active ultrasonic pulse technique when practicing 60 cycles of sulphate attack, freeze-thaw, and wetting-drying. The decline in the USPV through the mentioned durability cycles will be detected with the aid of PUNDIT apparatus and modeled.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Portland Cement

Sulfate resistant Portland cement SRC and ordinary Portland cement OPC with a commercial name of (Tasluga, Al-jesser) were implemented in this investigation. The physical property of the cement is demonstrated in Table 1 while their chemical composition is shown in Table 2. The test results show that the cement conforms to the provisions of Iraqi specification No. 5, [28].

Table 1: Physical properties of Portland cement.

Type of cement	OPC		SRC	
Physical property	Test result	IQS, No.5, 1984 Limits	Test result	IQS, No.5, 1984 Limits
Specific surface area, Blain method, (m ² /Kg)	357	>230	258	> 250
Setting time, Vicat's Method				
Initial setting ,(minutes)	155	≥ 45	90	≥ 45
Final setting , (minutes)	285	≤ 600	250	≤ 600
Compressive strength (N/mm ²)				
3- Days	15.8	≥ 15	18.3	≥ 15
7- Days	23.3	≥ 23	23.8	≥ 23

Table 2: Chemical composition of Portland cement.

Chemical composition	Type of portland cement	
	OPC	SRC
CaO	55	60.6
SiO ₂	18.3	21.6
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.28	4.76
Al ₂ O ₃	5.88	4.19
MgO	1.93	2.73
SO ₃	1.87	2.04
C ₃ A	10.0	3.06
C ₃ S	35	42.6
C ₂ S	26.2	29.9
C ₄ AF	9.97	14.4
Loss on Ignition	3.26	1.94
Insoluble residue	0.15	0.92
Lime saturation factor	0.89	0.86

Coarse and Fine Aggregates

Crushed gravel with a nominal maximum size of (19 mm) was brought from Nibae region and fine aggregates was obtained from brought from Al-Ukhaider were implemented in this work. The aggregates

were washed, then air dried and separated into different sizes by sieving. The properties of aggregates are shown in Table 3. The test was conducted according to ASTM, C-127, [29] and ASTM C-128, [30]

Table 3: Properties of coarse and fine aggregates.

Type of aggregate	Specific gravity	Water absorption	SO ₃ %
Coarse aggregates	2.650	1.0	0.07
Fine aggregates	2.4	3.24	0.45

Water

The water used in RCC mixes was tap water in the Baghdad area. This water was also used for curing.

Combined Gradation of Coarse and Fine Aggregate

Dense gradation usually used for asphalt concrete pavement base course in Iraq with 25 mm of nominal maximum size has been adopted for this investigation as per SCR-B-R-9, [31].

Fig. 1: Implemented gradation of aggregates.

Mix Design of roller compacted concrete RCC

Modified compaction of the aggregate mixture was conducted according to ASTM-D1557, [32] and the maximum dry density and optimum moisture content was obtained. Five different percentages of cement content were used (10, 12, 14, 16, 18) % by weight of air-dry aggregate. Various percentage of water content with a range of (4–11) % of air-dry aggregate with 1% increment were added. The dry density-moisture content relationships were constructed. Details on the mixture density are published elsewhere, Sarsam et al., [33].

Preparation of RCC samples

The designed water-cement-aggregates mixture was placed in the slab mold with size (380× 380 × 100) mm and subjected to initial compaction of three cycles of (8 seconds) vibration of 50 Hz frequency on a vibrating table with 30 seconds time interval, then the mold was fixed in front of the roller compactor device and subjected to three stages of rolling based on the work done by Sarsam, [34], and Abdulrahim, [35]. For each stage, 10 passes were applied. This number of passes is suitable to achieve the good rolling with low labor, and the rolling action is taken in (x-x) direction, then the same sequence has been repeated in the (y- y) direction as shown in Figure 2. The prepared slab samples are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 2: Roller compaction apparatus.

Fig. 3: Part of the RCC slab samples.

The first stage may represent the initial compaction in the field; a total load of 1.1 kg/cm width was applied with 10 passes of the roller in each direction. The second stage simulates the intermediate field compaction; a total load of 3.2 kg/cm width was applied with 10 passes of the roller in each direction. The final stage represents the finishing compaction in the field; a total load of 5.3kg/cm width was applied with 10 passes of the roller in each direction. A total of 12 slab samples were prepared. The samples were covered with polyethylene sheet and left to cure at room temperature of $30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours. The slab samples were removed from the mold

and immersed in the water for (28) days for curing at $30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. Beams specimens of (380×80×100) mm were obtained from the slab samples with the aid of diamond saw. A total of 36 beam specimens were obtained and tested in triplicate; the average value of the test was considered for analysis. The accepted standard deviation was 5 % for the testing results for such a limited testing program. Figure 4 demonstrated sawing of slab sample to obtain beam specimens and part of the obtained beams. The raw data of testing was obtained from Sarsam et al., [36] and analyzed through this work.

Fig. 4: Obtaining beam specimens from the slab samples.

Sulfate Attack cycles

Resistance of RCC samples to disintegration by immersion in a saturated solution of sodium sulfate was implemented according to ASTM C-88-99, [37] procedure for aggregate soundness except that beam specimens which were obtained from the casted RCC slab samples were used. Triplicate beam specimens were immersed in saturated sodium sulphate solution for 24 hours then air dried after each immersion cycle. This procedure was repeated for 60 cycles.

Freeze-thaw cycles: The freezing-thawing cycles was carried out according to ASTM C-666-97, procedure B, [38]. Freezing and thawing tests was started by placing triplicate beam specimens from each mix in the thawing water at a temperature of $30 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ for 150 minutes.

The specimens removed from water and placed in deep freezer at temperature ($-11 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) for four hours as the beginning of the freezing phase of the cycle. This procedure is repeated for 60 cycles of freezing and thawing.

Wetting-Drying Cycles: The RCC specimens were subjected to cycles of wetting and drying in the light of the procedures adopted by many research works, Ahmed, [39]; and Sarsam, [40].

The cycles are started by placing triplicate beam specimens from each mix in the oven at a temperature of 70°C for 24 hours; Then, it is removed from oven and immersed in water bath for 24 hours at 25°C . The alternate immersion and drying of specimens are repeated for 60 cycles.

Testing for active ultrasonic pulse velocity with Pundit

The active ultrasonic pulse velocity technology was adopted to measure the USPV with the aid of PUNDIT according to ASTM C-597, [41].

The pundit with frequency 55KHz and accuracy of 0.1, was implemented to measure the USPV through RCC beam specimens. The implemented PUNDIT is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Active ultrasonic pulse velocity technique with the aid of PUNDIT.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Sulphate Attack Cycles

Figure 6 demonstrates the deterioration of concrete quality in terms of decline in USPV as the sulphate attack cycles proceeds. It can be observed that specimens prepared with SRC exhibits better performance and higher USPV when compared with specimens prepared with OPC. At failure, the USPV declined by (8,

12.5, and 19.1) % and (7.2, 11.3, and 19.1) % for OPC and SRC for mixtures prepared with (16, 12, and 10) % cement respectively as compared with the control mixtures before the start of the sulphate attack cycles. The USPV at failure of the SRC mixtures is higher than that of the OPC mixtures by (15.3, 14.2, and 9) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively.

Fig. 6: Deterioration of RCCP due to sulphate attack cycles.

However, the USPV for the control mixtures prepared with SRC is higher than that of the control mixtures prepared with OPC by (10, 8.7, and 0.9) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively. Similar behavior was reported by Anwar et al., [15]. The rate of decline in the USPV is more gentle for specimens prepared with SRC when compared with that of specimens prepared with OPC. As far as the cement content is concerned, significant variations in the USPV could

be found as the cement content rises from (10 to 16) % regardless of the cement type. Higher USPV indicate lower voids and microcracks in the mixture. For OPC mixture, the USPV increased by (47, and 64.2) % before and after the sulphate attack cycles respectively when the cement content rises from (10 to 16) %, while for SRC mixture, the USPV increased by (61.7, and 75) % before and after the sulphate attack cycles respectively when the cement content rises from (10 to 16)

%. It can be revealed that the cement content plays a significant role in the mechanical properties and components of concrete. Similar findings were reported by Yu et al., [13]. No significant stages of deterioration could be detected of concrete mixtures under sulfate attack conditions. Table 4 shows the linear mathematical models of the effect of sulphate attack cycles on the USPV through the concrete samples. The linear mathematical models can accurately characterize the degree of

concrete degradation under sulfate attack. High coefficients of determination are observed, indicating an excellent representation of the models to the sulphate attack issue. Zhao et al., [16] stated that exponent models were found to represent such deterioration. However, Zhao et al., [23] reported that shear cracks through failure process of concrete gradually increases with the increase in cycle time.

Table 4. Modeling the influence of sulphate attack cycles

Type of cement	OPC		SRC	
Cement content %	Mathematical model	R ²	Mathematical model	R ²
16	$Y = - 0.0070 X + 5.035$	0.998	$Y = - 0.006 X + 5.4767$	0.995
12	$Y = - 0.0083 X + 4.010$	0.999	$Y = - 0.007 X + 4.3333$	0.999
10	$Y = - 0.0097 X + 3.363$	0.999	$Y = - 0.008 X + 3.3450$	0.998

Y = Ultrasonic pulse velocity (mm/microseconds); X = Number of sulphate attack cycles

Freeze-Thaw cycles

Understanding of freeze-thaw damage characteristics of concrete can enhance its performance through degradation and damage status for concrete. Figure 7 exhibits the deterioration of concrete quality in terms of decline in USPV as the freeze-thaw cycles proceeds. It can be observed that specimens prepared with SRC cement shows also better performance and higher USPV when compared with specimens prepared with

OPC. At failure, the USPV declined by (7, 10, and 14.7) % and (3.6, 9, and 11.7) % for OPC and SRC for mixtures prepared with (16, 12, and 10) % cement respectively as compared with the control mixtures before the start of the freeze-thaw cycles. The USPV at failure of the SRC mixtures is higher than that of the OPC mixtures by (15.3, 11.1, and 3.4) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively.

Fig. 7: Deterioration of RCCP due to freeze-thaw cycles.

However, the USPV for the control mixtures prepared with SRC is higher than that of the control mixtures prepared with OPC by (10, 10, and 0.9) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively. Toutouchi et al., [9] reported similar results and stated that such decline in the USPV is due to increasing percentages of possible weight loss of concrete after disintegration through the freeze-thaw cycles. Significant variations in the USPV were observed as the cement content rises from (10 to 16) % regardless of the cement type. Higher USPV indicate lower voids and microcracks in the mixture. For OPC mixture, the USPV increased by (47, and 58.6) % before and after the freeze-thaw cycles respectively when the cement content rises from (10 to 16) %, while for SRC mixture, the USPV increased by (61.7, and 75) % before and after the freeze-thaw cycles respectively when the cement content rises from (10 to 16) %. Such behavior could be attributed to the fact that with the increase of freeze-thaw cycles number, more serious spalling of the concrete surface could be expected, the rate of mass loss increases, indicating more obvious internal cracks of the concrete and more serious damage as

reported by Cao et al., [24]. However, elastic modulus, accumulative energy in concrete, and brittleness of concrete specimens declined gradually with the increase in freeze-thaw cycles as reported by Lian et al., [20]; and Xu et al., [21]. As the freeze-thaw cycles time increased, possible shear cracks through failure process of concrete gradually increases as revealed by Zhao et al., [23]. Damage characteristics due to Freeze–thaw cycles were evaluated by Lv et al., [19] through mass loss analysis, and ultrasonic pulse velocity testing. A parabola fitting pattern which represent the relationships between ultrasonic wave velocity, and freeze–thaw cycles was recommended. Table 5 demonstrates the linear mathematical models of the effect of freeze-thaw cycles on the USPV through concrete samples. High coefficients of determination are observed, indicating an excellent representation of the models to the freeze-thaw issue. The freeze–thaw damage was also evaluated by Park et al., [22] and a correlation was established for assessing the damage at the early stages and at later stages as the damage progressed. A reliable results were produced.

Table 5: Modelling the influence of freezing-thawing cycles.

Type of cement	OPC		SRC	
Cement content %	Mathematical model	R ²	Mathematical model	R ²
16	Y = - 0.0057 X + 5.033	0.998	Y = - 0.0047 X + 5.4733	0.998
12	Y = - 0.0063 X + 4.013	0.999	Y = - 0.0053 X + 4.3333	0.998
10	Y = - 0.0073 X + 3.363	0.999	Y = - 0.006 X + 3.3433	0.999
Y = Ultrasonic pulse velocity (mm/microseconds); X = Number of freeze-thaw cycles				

Wetting-Drying cycles

Figure 8 demonstrates the deterioration of concrete quality in terms of decline in USPV as the wet-dry cycles proceeds. It can be observed that specimens prepared with SRC shows also better performance and higher USPV when compared with specimens prepared with OPC. At failure, the USPV declined by (10, 12.5, and 14.7)

% and (7.2, 11.3, and 14.7) % for OPC and SRC for mixtures prepared with (16, 12, and 10) % cement respectively as compared with the control mixtures before the start of the wet-dry cycles. The USPV at failure of the SRC mixtures is higher than that of the OPC mixtures by (13.3, 11.4, and 3.5) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively. However, the

USPV for the control mixtures prepared with SRC is higher than that of the control mixtures prepared with OPC by (10, 7.5, and 0.9) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively. Such deterioration of strength of the concrete which was evaluated and analyzed through an USPV technique indicates that the cumulative energy of concrete declines with the progression of wet-dry cycles. Wang et al., [25] reported similar findings. The rate of decline in the USPV is more gentle for specimens prepared with SRC when compared with the sharp rate of decline of specimens prepared with OPC. As far as the cement content is concerned, significant variations in the USPV could be found as the cement content rises from (10 to 16) % regardless of the cement type. Higher USPV indicate lower voids and microcracks in the mixture. For OPC

mixture, the USPV increased by (47, and 60.7) % before and after the wet-dry cycles respectively when the cement content rises from (10 to 16) %, while for SRC mixture, the USPV increased by (61.7, and 75.8) % before and after the wet-dry cycles respectively when the cement content rises from (10 to 16) %. It can be revealed that the cement content plays a significant role in the mechanical properties and components of concrete. Similar findings were reported by Saliba et al., [26]. The test results declared that the degradation of concrete starts during the initial cycles of wet-dry while surface cracks of the RCC specimens were visible. Considerable loss of mechanical properties of concrete is expected after 60 wet-dry cycles. Such behavior agrees with the work reported by Zhu et al., [27].

Fig. 8: Deterioration of RCCP due to Wet-Dry cycles.

Table 6 demonstrates the linear mathematical models of the effect of wetting-drying cycles on the USPV through the concrete samples. High coefficients of determination are observed, indicating an excellent representation of the models to the wetting-drying issue.

Table 6: Modelling the influence of Wetting-Drying cycles.

Type of cement	OPC		SRC	
Cement content %	Mathematical model	R ²	Mathematical model	R ²
16	Y = - 0.0085 X + 5.035	0.998	Y = - 0.0065 X + 5.475	0.998
12	Y = - 0.0083 X + 4.013	0.999	Y = - 0.0077 X + 4.333	0.999
10	Y = - 0.0082 X + 3.355	0.998	Y = - 0.0073 X + 3.350	0.993
Y = Ultrasonic pulse velocity (mm/microseconds); X = Number of wet-dry cycles				

CONCLUSIONS

The following remarks could be concluded on the basis and limitations of testing program and materials.

1. At failure, the USPV declined by (8, 12.5, and 19.1) % and (7.2, 11.3, and 19.1) % for OPC and SRC for mixtures prepared with (16, 12, and 10) % cement respectively as compared with the control mixtures before the start of the sulphate attack cycles.
2. The USPV at failure of the SRC mixtures is higher than that of the OPC mixtures by (15.3, 14.2, and 9) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively after practicing sulphate attack cycles.
3. At failure, the USPV declined by (7, 10, and 14.7) % and (3.6, 9, and 11.7) % for OPC and SRC for mixtures prepared with (16, 12, and 10) % cement respectively as compared with the control mixtures before the start of the freeze-thaw cycles.
4. The USPV at failure of the SRC mixtures is higher than that of the OPC mixtures by (15.3, 11.1, and 3.4) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively after practicing freeze-thaw cycles.
5. At failure, the USPV declined by (10, 12.5, and 14.7) % and (7.2, 11.3, and 14.7) % for OPC and SRC for mixtures prepared with (16, 12, and 10) % cement respectively as compared with the control mixtures before the start of the wet-dry cycles.
6. The USPV at failure of the SRC mixtures is higher than that of the OPC mixtures by (13.3, 11.4, and 3.5) % for (16, 12, and 10) % cement content respectively after practicing wet-dry cycles.
7. The obtained linear mathematical models can accurately characterize the degree of concrete degradation under sulfate attack, freeze-thaw, and wet-dry cycles.

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